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Interactions between the communities of *Les Herbonautes* and *Die Herbonauten*

Observation notes

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Introduction

Citizen sciences are taking a growing part in transcribing natural history scientific collections. Opening digitized labels to the general public is not only to complement data produced institutionally, it allows to highlight the collections and their use for science and biodiversity.

Designed in 2012 by the *Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle*, Paris after the mass digitisation of this institution herbarium, *Les Herbonautes* gathered an active community over its 6 years of existence. The French national infrastructure ReColNat developed a more flexible version and opens the source code to the biodiversity community. *Die Herbonauten* was launched by the *Botanischer Garten und Botanisches Museum Berlin* in 2018, based on the French platform code. These two linguistic versions of the herbonauts systems are managed independently one from another, each building its community separately.

During ICEDIG project, a pilot project has been held on several citizen science platform, including *Les Herbonautes* and *Die Herbonauten*. On the French as on the German platform, the project was held during summer 2018. The two synchronized missions brought to light some unexpected exchanges between the two user communities.

Despite the two platform having contacts mainly for technical matters, the two communities have been seen communicating with one another, and exchanging information.

Case study: mission ICEDIG

Context

The task 4.2 of the ICEDIG project, entitled Data quality, verification, validation and enrichment of data, aimed at checking the quality and efficiency of different transcription methods. A pilot project was run to produce comparative data on several media. Amongst these media *Les Herbonautes* (LH) and *Die Herbonauten* (DH) were tested. As for all the solutions tested, the same of herbarium specimen images was used. It is a set of 1377 images from 7 European herbaria (BR, K, BM, B, E, P and TU), the one used for this project is an earlier version of the one described in Dillen et al. (2019). Results of this pilot project are described by Phillips et al. (2019) in ICEDIG deliverable 4.2.

This pilot project aimed, amongst other things, to test the influence of label language on the transcription efficiency.

The test mission was launched on LH on 22/06/2018. During the 110 days of its duration, 26.890 single contributions (answer to a question) were provided by 41 contributors (47 users joined the mission, 6 of them not contributing). Detailed statistics and contribution are available on the platform website (<http://lesherbonautes.mnhn.fr/missions/11755959>).

Figure 1: Contributions to the mission “Un aperçu de la diversité des collections européennes” distribution through time. a. cumulated / b. daily.

The Figure 1 depicts the contribution to the mission through time. The accumulated graph (Figure 1a) shows a regular growth of the contribution through time without major changes. The daily amount of contribution graph (Figure 1b) shows only two major irregularities:

- The first one on the 4th and 5th of July, a hit over 1.000 contributions per day. This is related to the end of the other mission on the platform at the time (Rubus reloaded). Although this late mission was not over before the 16th of July, all the specimens were completed at this time. Together with the end of technical issues on the website, the ICEDIG mission did gathered all the activity of the platform for a few weeks until the launch of the mission “*La Scammonée aiguë*”, on the 26th of July. A slight drop in the daily contribution is visible around this last mission launch, due to curiosity of users.
- The second peak, between the 28th of August and the 2nd of September does not seems to have a single reason. It arrived just after the release of a correction on the image viewer. However, it corresponds to a drop in the contribution to the other mission (“*La Scammonée aiguë*”). It is most probably due to exchanges between users.

Outside these two peaks, the contribution rate on this particular mission does follow the rhythm of the one of the missions online at the same time. To note that no particular weekly contribution pattern can be drawn from this graph.

Figure 2: contributions to the mission per user account

The Figure 2 depicts the percentage of total contributions per user. As it is a common trend in citizen science project (Rotman et al. 2014, Livermore et al. 2015, Zacklad and Chupin 2015, Geoghegan et al. 2016, Chupin 2017, Le Bras and Chagnoux 2018), we can clearly see the major users. One user having done 25% of the contribution, and 5 users (amongst the 41) having committed over 75% of the contribution. Interesting thing here is that the main contributor (Graouscy) is as well the main bridge user between LH community and DH one.

Observations on *les Herbonautes* Forum

The following observations were conducted on the mission's main thread on LH. Due to a technical issue, no comparison was however possible with DH thread as the discussion history was lost after version upgrade.

On LH, during the 110 days of the mission, 73 messages were exchanged on the main thread. 11 users did involve in it (23,4% of the mission members). The amount of message and of contribution per user account for these 11 users is visible on Figure 3. The 4 biggest contributors and 7 out of the 10 main contributor to the mission take part in the forum thread. The 3 accounts with no contributions are actually the account of the members of the management team. Users talking on the main thread are mostly main users of the mission,

and the management team. An interesting thing however is that the second main contributor to the thread (Suedonaute) did not committed many contributions to the mission compared to other users on the thread (126 contributions, 18th contributor). This user is one of the major users since the beginning of the platform. The behaviour recorded on this forum thread/contribution amount seems however to correspond to what he's been doing lately. From main contributor, he shifted its position from CS volunteer to group leader. He's helping the professional team to manage the community of the missions.

Figure 3: Amount of comments on the mission main thread and of contribution per user

Figure 4: Classification of forum comment subject

We classified the 73 messages on the thread depending on their content (Figure 4):

- Details query (14 messages). During the beginning of the mission, the platform did experience a technical issue over specimen commenting. Users then used the main thread to ask other users to modify or justify their contribution.
- Debate (13 messages). We here counted the messages where user debates over various subjects (cf. below)
- Management (11 messages). These are the messages let by the three managing accounts giving general information to the community.
- Technical issue (10 messages). These are query mainly addressed to the management team concerning the technical issues faced during the mission. These issues were partly due to a version issue making it difficult for us to input data not in the ReCoINat portal, and a viewer issue making it hard for the users to visualise the specimen. These issues were solved with the version 2.1 (more detail available on GitHub).
- General comment (8 messages). We counted as general comment messages that were of general matter around the mission itself. cf. below for more detail
- Questions (3 messages) and Instructions (4 messages) about the proceeding. We counted here the instruction about the proceeding given by the non-professional users. Two of them where answering the three questions query messages. Two other messages were giving general instruction about the proceeding.
- Resource giving (3 messages). Not much message where actually about resources giving, but they were giving all the possible tricks to find the data (cf. below)
- Discouragement (3 messages). These three messages were posted one after the other, when three amongst the main users decided to draw back their participation to the mission until a solution to the technical issue was found. This correspond to the first drop in participation around the 2nd of July (Figure 1b)

- Cheering (2 messages). These are message cheering up the community and thanking the management for having set a mission with specimen from several European herbaria
- Socialization (2 messages). These are message where users socialized (“I come from [...]?”)

Debating on a CS platform forum?

This particular mission was an unusual one for the users, and they understood straight away the mission was about testing their work. They very fast started to debate over the fact that using external resources (cf. below) would be cheating and would modify the result of the analyse. The management team had then to reveal very fast the purpose of the mission, and to promise them a more detailed explanation by the end of the mission.

A second source of debate, more common on LH was about procedure detail. Sometime not very clear for some users, it turned into a debate.

General comments

The general comments were showing the interest of the users for this particular mission. One user asked for other versions of the Herbonautes (other than German, since she’s talking only English and Spanish). Several comment that the mission is fun because multi-lingual, and that it’s such a pity the technical issues makes it so difficult to take part. Some comment on the fact that the results of the study behind the mission are already know, as LH is a known place. Comments were querying about the general aim of the study.

In middle of August, some users wondered why the contribution didn’t seemed to progress, and another answered that probably some “stalkers are just watching without transcribing”.

Ressources exchange

Within two messages, Graouscy and Suedonaute shared to everyone the URL of the web search engine of all the collections involved in this mission. The third resource giving message was about the URL of the same specimen in the LH mission and in the DH one. This last message was the only one of its sorts on the general thread, but Graouscy has been sharing this type of information on specimen related threads on both the missions (cf. below).

It is important to keep in mind the Herbonautes are commonly using the web application of Paris herbarium to compare the specimen they are transcribing with other already transcribed. They also use The Plant List and Wikipedia to enrich their data. This is common practice for professional transcription, the CS just do the same.

Exchanges with *Die Herbonauten* on this mission

One of the most interesting events of this particular mission, shared on both LH and DH platform was the somehow unexpected exchanges of information and knowledge from one community to another.

A major Bridge User

The first user of the LH mission, Graouscy (6.670 contributions), also happen to be the second biggest contributor of the mission on DH (6.329 contributions). She openly presents herself as a bi-lingual user, and is very active on both the communities since DH launch. As mentioned above, she shared on the specimen linked forum the same image on the other platform and did help on DH with French translation. It seems she was filling the same specimen on both platforms using the search engine to select the one she wanted.

Other trans-platform users

Even if not at the same level of implication as Graouscy, other users take openly part on both communities, and did took part to this mission. One can as well notice in the DH community users with singular behaviour: taking part only to this one mission, and committing only data from Paris and Kew specimen. Nothing allow us to confirm they are LH users, but this behaviour is singular enough to be noticed.

Other observations

Alongside with Graouscy, users amongst the main user on LH are openly being active on both sides, since DH launching. Obviously, we can only here talk about the users having the same or really similar alias, or having clearly mentioned their name on both the interfaces. As such other bridge users do transfer knowledge from LH to DH community. One can consider as such Protea, but as well Suedonaute (not currently active on DH since several months).

A major German user have been reported to have come to take part to LH following DH service shutdown for upgrading during fall 2018. This user, Zemach, finished the DH ICEDIG mission with the most contribution, 6.338 (9 more than Graouscy). He was a major user on DH since its beginning with over 25.000 contribution within less than a year. Since he joined LH it has become a regular one on the French platform as well and is now being active on both platforms. He is exchanging regularly with LH “talking users”. Introduced to the other by Graouscy being clearly identified as a DH originated user, he is being advised consequently

by the community. This particular user constitutes then another major bridge between the two communities having come from the other way (DH to LH).

Following this mention, we operated a survey over the new account created on LH between the 1st of January 2018 and the 28th of February 2019. We aimed at detecting the eventuality of a report of user from Germany while DH was down. We based our study on domain from the email-addresses and country mention of the new user account. We were able to determine a country of origin for 184 accounts out of the 355 new creation (51,83%).

- With no surprises the vast majority of the account were from France (145 accounts - 78,80%).
- The second origin of creation of account was from Ecuador (18 accounts - 9,78%). This is linked to a specific project conducted together with the Private Technical University of Loja. All of these accounts were linked with students following a course there. All of the account creations were done between April 2018 and August 2019, and took part to a single mission in Spanish (Descubriendo Coccoloba y el apasionante mundo de los árboles tropicales <http://lesherbonautes.mnhn.fr/missions/10303441>).
- The third country origin for the account was Germany (6 account creations - 3,26%). On the contrary with the case for Ecuador, no precise tendency can be drawn for these account creations. If any, the report of community from DH to LH during the shutdown of the German platform was quantitatively small (3 accounts creation within the 3 months). However, and despite the language difference, and no particular institutional will to recruit from one community to another, exchanges spontaneously occur.
- The other countries of origin were: New Caledonia (different domain name than France, 4 account creation - 2,17%), Canada (4 account creation - 2,17%), Denmark (2 creations - 1,09%), and finally, United States, Portugal, Spain and Switzerland (each 1 creation - 0,54%).

Several mission in Spanish have been run on LH. LH community did massively take part to these missions, even now they're not being curated in French. The community is then somehow used to multilingualism even now the main language on the platform is French. However, despite the efforts made by ReColNat team to engage students on the mission, there is no evidence of a long-lasting Spanish speaking sub-community on LH. Spanish speakers that specifically take part to the Spanish curated missions resume their participation once the Spanish mission is over, and do not come back on the next one, as they are separate by some months. It then tells us that it requires continuous effort to keep an active community: one need to have permanently at least one mission/project running, and it is probably more efficient to have a tool translated in the relevant language (i.e. a separate platform as DH).

Conclusion

The ICEDIG pilot project on transcription quality considered each platform as a separate tool. We did not expect any interactions between them. But a careful study of the forum thread show that Citizen Science platforms should not to be considered as tools but rather as human communities gathered around a tool.

As human being does, users seek solutions to the issues they encounter, and they transmit their solutions to other when appropriate communication tools such as forum are provided to them. This experience showed us as well the great importance of this forum for the community building, as much as for the management teams to understand what is going on the platform. It gives as well the possibility to historical user to keep being active even when not committing data. For instance, Suedonaute spontaneously helped managing this mission on LH without committing much transcriptions as he does regularly.

The languages were considered as a boundary for users. We now know that if it may be a barrier for individual understanding, it is not for community engagement, as what we here referred as “bridge users” do transfer information, expertise, resources from one language community to another. We suspect the LH and DH users to have developed a special bond to the platform, and, for the ones understanding German and French to be enjoying committing data to one or another platform. As a result, the Herbonauts community should now be considered as a multilingual meta-community. It is to be expected that this community will grow strong of other languages if new platforms are created with the open code.

Seed for new communities lies within the existing platforms. During this mission, users have been asking the management team about existing Herbonauts platforms in other languages than French and German. The experience built by LH and DH communities would most probably transfer to other new tool created despite language barriers and that without the management to have great effort to do.

This experience show clearly that this meta-community of users is much more ready to work together than the platforms management teams expected.

References

- Chupin L (2017) Enjeux communicationnels de la conception de dispositifs de médiation documentaire augmentée pour les herbiers numérisés. École doctorale Abbé Grégoire Available from: https://xupi.eu/these_lisa_chupin/these_chupin.pdf (June 4, 2018).
- Dillen M, Groom Q, Chagnoux S, Güntsch A, Hardisty A, Haston E, Livermore L, Runnel V, Schulman L, Willemse L, Wu Z, Phillips S (2019) A benchmark dataset of herbarium specimen images with label data. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 7. doi: 10.3897/BDJ.7.e31817
- Geoghegan H, Dyke A, Pateman R, West S, Everett G (2016) Understanding motivations for citizen science. Final report on behalf of UKEOF. University of Reading, Stockholm Environment Institute (University of York) and University of the West of England, 120pp.
- Le Bras G, Chagnoux S (2018) Evaluation of Existing Volunteer Transcription Systems. Zenodo doi: 10.5281/zenodo.2578938
- Livermore L, Tweddle J, French L, Phillips S, Robinson L, Smith VS (2015) Making molehills out of mountains: crowdsourcing digital access to natural history collections. Synthesys Available from: <http://www.synthesys.info/wp-content/uploads/2014/01/NA3-Del.-3.4-Crowdsourcing-report-Phase-2.pdf>.
- Phillips S, Dillen M, Groom Q, Green L, Weech M-H, Wijkamp N (2019) Report on New Methods for Data Quality Assurance, Verification and Enrichment. ICEDIG/DiSSCo. Deliverable 4.2 Available from: https://icedig.eu/sites/default/files/deliverable_d4.2_icedig_data_quality_in_transcription.pdf.
- Rotman D, Hammock J, Preece J, Hansen D, Boston C, Bowser A, He Y (2014) Motivations Affecting Initial and Long-Term Participation in Citizen Science Projects in Three Countries. In: *iSchools*. doi: 10.9776/14054
- Zacklad M, Chupin L (2015) Le crowdsourcing scientifique et patrimonial à la croisée de modèles de coordination et de coopération hétérogènes : le cas des herbiers numérisés. *Canadian Review of Information Science* 39: 308–328.

